

Studies on Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Ho(III) and Er(III) Chelates

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The rare-earth chelates of Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Ho(III) and Er(III) with O-(N- α -pyrrolideneimino)benzoic acid (H₂NBA) and 2-(α -2-oxopropylbenzylidene-imino)propanoic acid (H₂BAA), have been synthesised and subjected to spectral and magnetic studies. The magnetic study reveals their high-spin octahedral geometry. The bonding parameters have also been evaluated.

SEVERAL reactions of transition metals with Schiff bases have been studied¹⁻³. As an extension of the study, an attempt has been made to understand the spectral and magnetic behaviour of some lanthanon chelates. The results obtained are described in the present communication.

Experimental

The ligands were synthesised by refluxing equimolar ethanolic solution mixtures of benzoyl acetone with β -alanine and pyrole-2-carboxaldehyde with anthranilic acid, respectively. The product was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to get the pure compound. The purity of the ligands was confirmed by m p. and elemental analyses.

All the reagents used were of analytical grade (E. Merck or B.D.H.). Instruments employed were the same as reported earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The solid lanthanon chelates were prepared by the literature procedure⁵ and their composition

may be represented by [HML₂] where M=Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Ho(III) or Er(III) and LH₂=H₂NBA or H₂BAA. These compounds behave as weak-electrolytes as revealed by their very low molar conductance in dioxane. The magnetic moment values obtained experimentally indicate the presence of 2, 3, 5, 4 and 3 numbers of unpaired electrons in Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Ho(III) and Er(III) chelates, respectively. These values indicate that they exist as monomer and suggest that the orbital contribution is almost quenched by the crystalline field.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectral data of the chelates are given in Table 1. These data were analysed to find out the application of the nephelauxetic effect on lanthanide series. The nephelauxetic parameters were calculated by Jorgensen's method⁶. The (1- β) values are used to estimate bonding parameter known as Sinha's co-valency parameter⁷. The average values of the parameter are less than unity which indicate weak co-valent bonding. The $b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is another bonding parameter

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND BONDING PARAMETERS OF H₂BAA AND H₂NBA CHELATES

Ion	H ₂ BAA chelates in DMSO in cm ⁻¹	H ₂ NBA chelates in DMSO in cm ⁻¹	J-levels	(1- β) × 10 ⁻²		δ (%)		$b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (× 10 ⁻¹)	
				H ₂ BAA	H ₂ NBA	H ₂ BAA	H ₂ NBA	H ₂ BAA	H ₂ NBA
Pr(III)	22260	22280	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	0.93	0.85	0.9489	0.8137	0.06	0.03
	21120	21140	→ ³ P ₁	0.50	0.84	0.5025	0.3970	0.07	0.07
	20610	20630	→ ³ P ₀	0.67	0.68	0.6846	0.5831	0.05	0.04
Nd(III)	16930	16850	→ ¹ D ₂	0.41	0.89	0.4217	0.3735	0.06	0.05
	19480	19520	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁶ G ₃ , ⁸ H _{9/2}	0.20	0.15	0.2101	0.1901	0.03	0.03
	18920	18890	→ ⁴ F _{7/2}	0.42	0.38	0.4318	0.3911	0.06	0.06
	17250	17220	→ ⁴ F _{5/2}	0.29	0.21	0.2908	0.2101	0.03	0.02
	14475	14500	→ ⁴ G _{5/2}	1.20	0.98	1.2145	1.1260	0.07	0.05
	13225	13200	→ ⁴ G _{7/2}	1.31	1.02	1.3276	1.1376	0.08	0.07
	12825	12855	→ ⁴ G _{9/2}	1.40	1.31	1.4198	1.2190	0.08	0.06
Sm(III)	24800	24780	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁶ F _{9/2}	0.41	0.35	0.4116	0.3816	0.04	0.03
	23720	23750	→ ⁶ P _{5/2}	0.63	0.53	0.6339	0.3680	0.05	0.03
	21570	21470	→ ⁴ I _{13/2}	0.37	0.29	0.3730	0.2918	0.04	0.02
Ho(III)	22350	22300	⁴ I ₉ → ⁶ G ₆	0.57	0.42	0.5698	0.4568	0.05	0.04
	19090	19060	→ ⁶ G ₄	0.90	0.78	0.9128	0.8316	0.06	0.05
	15770	15730	→ ⁶ F ₈	0.87	0.71	0.8630	0.7360	0.06	0.03
Er(III)	10550	10570	⁴ F _{15/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}	0.78	0.68	0.7732	0.6328	0.06	0.05
	18800	10820	→ ⁴ I _{13/2}	0.32	0.29	0.3176	0.1281	0.04	0.03
	20950	20930	→ ⁴ F _{7/2}	0.59	0.48	0.5886	0.4836	0.05	0.04

which measures the amount of 4f ligand mixing as given by Henrie and Chopin⁸. The values of $(1-\beta)$ and $b^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the present chelates show that the covalent contribution increases in the order $H_2BAA > H_2NBA$ chelates.

The bands observed in the case of Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Ho(III) and Er(III) chelates may be due to transitions from ground level 3H_4 , $^4H_{9/2}$, 5I_8 and $^4I_{15/2}$ to the excited J-levels of $4f^n$ configuration, respectively.

Infrared spectra: IR spectra of H_2NBA consist of three bands at 3310, 1625 and 2575 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{NH} , ν_{C-N} and ν_{COOH} , respectively. In the spectra of H_2BAA , four bands were observed at 2530, 3350, 1690 and 1600 cm^{-1} which corresponded to ν_{COOH} , ν_{OH} , ν_{C-C} and ν_{C-N} , respectively. In the two types of metal chelates ν_{C-N} was lowered from 1625 and 1600 cm^{-1} to 1590 and 1585 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating involvement of azomethine nitrogen in chelation. The IR spectra of lanthanon chelates display a greater separation of $\nu_{as(COO)}$ and $\nu_{s(COO)}$. The separation between $\nu_{symmetric}$ and $\nu_{asymmetric}$ (COO) vibration, $\Delta \nu_{(COO)}$, is an indication of the nature of carboxylate bonding to the metal⁹. It has been accepted that co-valent

character of M-O band increases with an increase of $\Delta \nu_{(COO)}$ values. In the case of H_2NBA chelates $\Delta \nu_{(COO)}$ value is 200 and for H_2BAA it is 220 which indicate co-valent nature of M-O bonding.

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References

1. R. P. MATHUR, K. G. SHARMA and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **28**, 29.
2. K. G. SHARMA, R. P. MATHUR and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 225.
3. K. G. SHARMA, R. P. MATHUR and R. K. MEHTA, *Proc. Ind. Natl. Sci. Acad.*, 1981, **47A**, 322.
4. C. P. GUPTA, N. K. SANKLA and R. K. MEHTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1392.
5. D. D. OZHA, B. R. SINGHVI and R. K. MEHTA, *Acta Chim. (Budapest)*, 1976, **88**, 63.
6. C. K. JORGENSEN, R. PAPPALARADO and E. RITTERSHAUS, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1964, **19a**, 424.
7. S. P. SINHA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 2205.
8. D. E. HENRIE and G. R. CHOPPIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 477.
9. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **83**, 4528 and references therein.